

“Impact of ATMs on Customer Satisfaction” (A Case Study of SBI in Kalaburagi District of Karnataka)

Dr.Srinivas Nainoor

Dept. of Commerce, Govt. First Grade College, KALAGI, Dist: Kalaburagi State; Karnataka

Corresponding Author- Dr.Srinivas Nainoor

Introduction

The forces of globalization and technology have resulted in increasing integration of economics across the world. Today, banks are no more competing locally, but in the global market place. It is important for banks to adjust themselves to this new environment in the words of Karen Kaiser Clark: “Life is Change; Growth is Optional, Choose Wisely.” Today’s customers have a wider range of products to choose from. In order to service this ever-increasing customer demand, banks, which were highly branch focused, are concentrating on multi-channel delivery. This enables them to reach out to customers in any part of the world. Further, the one-size-fits all approach has been replaced with an approach based on customization and innovation.

In the word of Charles Darwin “It is not the strongest of the species that survive, nor the most intelligent, but the one most responsive to change” So to survive in this changing environment, banks should become more and more service oriented and ore and more technology oriented. If the banks are concerned with what the customers want, when they want and how they want, use of technology becomes inevitable .The use of technology will enable banks to enlarge their market share and also ensure customer satisfaction. T technology has changed banking forever and the banks should use technology as handmaiden for effectively delivering banking products to customers, especially corporates.

Modern banking services are becoming an important part of banking activity in the world. This is due to several factors, such as opening up of the economy, competition, internal re-external problems of size and scale, the range of financial services required and rapid advances in information technology, changing economic environment.

The new channels for delivering services to customers, especially corporate clients, which would remove the cumbersome, redundant and expensive paper process, are innovated by the bankers. Internet Banking, Tele banking, and much more services are offered to the customers, which save the customer time and money. By sitting in his home, customer can get the information of his banking transactions and even can transact from there.

Banking sector has developed another service to their customers known as automatic teller machines or automated teller machines facility (ATMs). An ATM (i.e., Automatic Teller Machine) is a device that allows Caerdholder to perform routine banking transaction without interacting with human teller. ATMs offer a broad range of banking transactions. The objective of ATM is to provide 24 hours, 365 days electronic banking services to the customers “any time, any where” in India and also to render uniform services at all locations.

ATM network system reaps many benefits. A well-positioned, high visibility ATM network system can be an effective marketing tool for bank’s image. To maintain competitive parity in banking industry banks must provide locatioanl round –the – year convenience of networked ATMs to is customers.

Review of Literature

Ravi Shanker, Professor, Indian Institute of Foreign Trade, New Delhi, in his book entitled “Services Marketeering” introduced the measures taken for the insurance sector reforms, identified the

impact of such reforms, and suggested marketing strategies to be adopted by the insurance companies in the emerging scenario. **Dr. Atul Bhatt** in his book titled “bank Marketing –marketing research and Indian Banks” explains the concept of bank, marketing, relevance of marketing in banks and suggested how marketing research can help a banking organization in sharpening consumer focus. **M.Y.Khan** in his book “Financial Services” classified financial services into two groups, first one is fund based and second one is fee based, and covers both type of services. A unique feature of the books that it provides a judicious mixture of theory and business practices of the contemporary Indian financial services sector.

Vimal Sukumar in his article on “Customer satisfaction” (20 ways to increase customer loyalty) explains in brief the significance of customer satisfaction and offers 20 ways to increase customer loyalty and improve the prospects of keeping customer longer.

Parimal Vyrs in her research paper entitled “Customer Satisfaction –as core competence explains clearly customers satisfaction in marketing theory and critically reviews the customer’s satisfaction Philosophy.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives set for present study:

1. To know the historical development of ATMs.
2. To study the working process of ATMs.

3. To examine the extent of customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction with ATM service given by banks.
4. To identify critical areas where customer dissatisfaction is very high.
5. To identify dissatisfier and to suggest remedial measures.

Research Methodology

The study is exclusively aimed at fact finding on the topic. The base for systematic and scientific study of any research work is methodology. The present research involved and organized sequence of activities as mentioned below.

1. Designing the Questionnaire
2. Collecting the data through
 - a. Primary Source
 - b. Secondary Source
3. Analyzing data and drawing inference

'Case Study' technique has been adopted as the methodology for in-depth study. The researcher has collected the information from 100 respondents. The respondents are selected on random sampling method.

Sources of Data

To meet the objectives of the study, the data has been collected from both primary and secondary sources. Responses of cardholders collected through structured questionnaire were the source of primary data in addition, information collected from the bank officials through personal interview method.

Pertaining to secondary data, the published books on banking services, magazines like Bank Quest and information collected from various websites are the main sources.

Techniques used in the Study

The plan of analysis and interpretation for analyzing data includes adoption of different techniques like percentages, ratio's etc 'Case study Technique is used to understand the study in a better way

ATM (A History)

Many inventors contribute to the history of an ATM. Don Wetzel invented first time the ATM

in the US. He was the co-patentee and chief conceptualist of the ATM, he thought an idea while maintaining in line at Dallas Bank. At that time (1968), he was vice-president of product planning at Docutel, the company that developed automated baggage handling equipment. The other two listed on patent were 'Tom Barnes' the chief mechanical Engineer and 'George Charstain' the electrical engineer. A working prototype came in 1969 and Docutel was issued a Patent in 1973. In US the first ATM was installed by Philadelphia national bank in 1969. By 1992 there were over 83,000 ATMs in US and 185 million cards had been issued. SBI is the leader in providing ATM services in Kalaburagi city. The total number of account holders in SBI is 11,000 out of which 4186 customers have the ATM cards. SBI is also not left behind in providing the ATM services to its customers in association with SBI. The total numbers of accountholders are 33,300 (including all 4 branches in the city), out of which only 3260 customers are using the ATM facility. As on 15th May 2004, the bank's network comprised 904 branches of which, 529 branches are in Andhra Pradesh, 174 branches in Maharashtra and 114 in Karnataka. The remaining branches spread in 11 states and two union territories. Customer occupies pivotal place in SBI, with a view to provide efficient service through translating technology, the bank computerised all the branches and installed 250 ATMs. Bank is shortly moving towards core banking solutions, internet banking facility multi-option deposit scheme, and depository services.

Business standard research bureau has conducted a survey on public, private and foreign bank to assess overall performance of bank on the basis of five parameter they are, profitability, safety, productivity, efficiency and growth. The top ten banks and their respective ranks in the primary are shown in below table.

TOP 10 BANKS

Rank 2002	Rank 2003	Name	Productivity Rank	Safety Rank	Profitability Rank	Growth Rank	Efficiency Rank
11	1	Andhra Pradesh	5	12	2	3	32
4	2	SB of Indore	16	6	1	18	25
3	3	Jammu & Kashmir Bank	37	6	4	32	13
1	4	Catholic Syrian Bank	29	48	3	34	53
42	5	Union bank of India	8	27	21	6	1
29	6	Indian Overseas Bank	25	7	12	25	18
23	8	Dev. Scheme Bank	17	5	19	42	21
9	9	SB of India	22	8	7	24	22

32	10	SB of Mysore	10	33	6	13	42
----	----	--------------	----	----	---	----	----

Source: Business Standard October 2023.

ATM's work

ATM has the following parts

1. **Card Reader:** the card reader captures the account information stored on the magnetic stripe on the back of the ATM. The host processor uses this information to route the transactions to the cardholder's bank.
2. **Keypad:** The keypad lets the cardholder tell the bank what kind of transaction are required (withdrawals, balance enquiry etc.) and for what amount withdrawals, etc. Federal law requires Personal Identification Number (PIN) to send to the host processor to form.
3. **Speaker:** The speaker provides the cardholder with auditory feedback when a key is pressed.
4. **Display screen:** The display screen prompts the cardholder through each step of the transaction process.
5. **Receipt printer:** The receipt printer provides the cardholder with a paper receipt of transaction.
6. **Cash dispenser:** The heart of an ATM is the safe and cash dispensing. The entire bottom portion of most of Small ATMs is safe that contains the cash.

An ATM is simply a data terminal with two inputs and four output devices like any other data terminal; the ATM has to connect to, and communicates through, a host processor. The host processor is analogous to an Internet Service Provider (ISP) in that it is the gateway through all the various ATM networks become available to the cardholders. The host processor may be owned by a bank or financial institution or it may be and by an Independent Service Providers.

The cash dispensing mechanism has an electric eye that counts each bill as it exit the dispenser. The bill count and all the information pertaining to a particular transaction is recorded in a journal. The journal information is printed out periodically and the machine owner maintains hard copies for two years. Whenever a cardholder has a dispute about a transaction, he can ask for a journal print out showing the transaction and then contact the host processor. Besides the electric eye that counts each bill, the cash dispensing mechanism also the sensor evaluates the thickness of each bill. Worned, torned, folded bills are diverted to a reject bin, the number of reject bills are also recorded so that the machine owner can be aware of the quality of bills that are being loaded into the machine.

ATM security:

Many banks recommended following tips for PIN and safe use of ATM.

1. Don't write down your PIN.

2. Make your PIN a series of letters or numbers that you can easily remember.
3. Avoid using birth dates, initials, house number or phone numbers etc.
4. Store your ATM card in your purse or wallet.
5. Get your card out before you approach the ATM.
6. Stand directly in front of the ATM keypad when typing your PIN. This prevents anyone waiting to use the machine from seeing your PIN.
7. After your transaction, take your receipt, card and money away.
8. If someone or something makes you uncomfortable, cancel your transaction and leave the machine immediately.
9. If you protect your PIN will protect your account.

Customer Satisfaction

Banking is a service industry and bankers are expected to give top priority to provide satisfactory service to their customers. Service is the end product of a bank's work and its success depends on the range and quality of the services. Customer satisfaction can be defined as;

1. A level of happiness resulting from a consumption experiences.
2. A cognitive state resulting from a process of evaluation of performance relative is previously established standards.
3. One step in a complex process involving prior attitude towards a service, a consumption experience resulting in a positive or negative disconfirmation of expectancies followed by feelings of satisfaction or dissatisfaction which mediate post consumption attitude.

Analysis of Primary data

Age-wise Distribution of Users:

It is clear from our field survey that customers of all age groups are users of ATM facility. Most of the ATM users are of middle age groups i.e., 25-35 years (46%) and also the young generation is adopting this (ATM) new facility quite abruptly the II largest number of ATM users lies in the age group less than 25 years. Where as the old age people (i.e., in the age group of 45 years onwards) they are reluctant to use the ATM facility. Only 12% of samples are falling under this category.

Education-wise Distribution of Users:

It is clear that most of the ATM users are graduates i.e., 67% of the sample consists graduates. This shows that educated people are heavy users of ATMs. Where as less educated or uneducated peoples are still sticks to the traditional system of banking.

Profession-wise Distribution of Users:

Most of the users (i.e., 30%) are business people. The second highest (i.e., 28%) users of ATM are student / unemployed person. The junior and senior officers amount to total 30% of ATM users. Whereas only 6% users are retired persons. This data shows that businesspersons, officials, students all are heavy users of ATM but only retired persons; clerical / sales person and housewife are reluctant to use ATM facility.

Distribution of Users according to their Annual Family Income:

61% of the users are belongs to a annual family income group of above Rs. 75,000. This shows that most of the ATM users are either upper middle class or top class people however the people who are having less than Rs.15,000/- annual family income are also using ATM service, such group mainly include students. This shows that income is not a criterion for adopting the new technology.

Factors which Motivated Customer to have the ATM card:

Bank employees play a vital role in motivating the customers to have the new facility like ATM. 49% of the users are motivated (or influenced) by the bank-employees to have the ATM facility. 33% of the users are self-motivated persons. They are all optimistic people who always search for new things and adopt them very easily. 18% of the users are influenced by their friends to take the ATM card.

Period of using the ATM Facility:

67% of the users are fall under the usage period of 1 to 6 months. This shows that the ATM facility is a new evolution in banking services and it is still newer to the city like Kalaburagi. Therefore, most of the users fall under user group of 1-6 months category.

Average visit to ATM:

79% of the users visit weekly to ATMs preferably on weekend. Hence, the demand of ATMs is much high at weekend than any other days. Most of the official and student fall under this category. 12% of the users visit ATMs monthly. A category of 9% of the users visit daily to ATMs they are mainly business people.

Awareness about the Restrictions that are there with ATM Usage:

85% of the users are aware about the restriction, which are there with ATM usage (like amount withdrawn/transaction, total number of transaction per day, time of collecting the money and card etc). They don't face any problem in using ATM's. Where as the 15% of users are unaware of the restriction about ATM usage, they face lot of problems while utilizing this facility.

Awareness about PIN (Personal Identification Number) Significance:

PIN is a very important element in ATM usage as anybody can withdraw the money by knowing this PIN (if the card is available to him). Hence, one should know the importance of the PIN. 97% of the users know the importance of PIN, while only 3% of users don't know this.

Whether the customer check this ATM transaction in their pass-book:

55% of the users felt that it is necessary to check their ATM transaction in the passbook, but 45% of the users are satisfied with balance statements, which are provided after transaction. They don't feel that the transaction should be crosschecked in their passbook.

Any Incidents wherein any Amount Debited to Customer's A/C without his knowledge due to use of ATM:

94% of the users don't have any such incidents where in any amount debited to their A/C without their knowledge, but 6 % of the users say that some amount debited to their A/C due to use of ATM without their knowledge. This is mainly due to service charges, which are charged for using the ATM.

Incidents where in ATM Restricted the Customer from Transacting:

91% of the users have no complaints against the usage of ATMs. These users have the good knowledge about the ATM usage. 9% of the users have the incidents where in ATM restricted them from transacting. This is mainly because the unawareness about ATM usage / functions.

Problems Faced by Customers with ATM due to its Malfunctioning:

76% of the users didn't face any problem with the ATM due to its malfunctioning. But 24% of the users face the problems with ATM, usage like network failure, technical problem of machine, no money in the ATM, power failure etc.

Whether the Guard is Trained Enough to Guide the Customer How to use ATM:

97% of the users feel that the guard at ATM is trained enough to guide them how to use ATM.

Satisfaction of Customers with the Availability of ATM Points:

55% of the users are very much satisfied with the number of ATMs in the city. They feel that supply is more 39% of the users feel that the supply is little bit less than the demand, where as 6 % of the users are highly dissatisfied with the number of ATMs in the city, they feel that the ATM should be located at all prime places like market, shopping complex, bus stand, railway stations etc.

Satisfaction of Customers with the Availability of Parking Space at ATM:

64% of the users are satisfied with the availability of parking space at ATMs. 27% of the users feel that the parking space available at ATMs is not enough and there should be some more space required for parking purpose where as 9% of the users are dissatisfied with the parking space at ATM

Rating of Users about ATM Usage:

58% of the users felt that the ATM service is good service. These users are satisfied with the ATM service. 36% of the users felt that the ATM is excellent service. There users are delighted with the usage of ATMs 6% of the users felt that the ATM is a fair service.

Findings:

1. The general awareness about the ATMs in Kalaburagi city is very less. Most of the people having their A/C's in banks but they are not using the ATM facility. Particularly female customers are highly heistant to adopt the new banking technology.
2. Students are more attracted towards the ATM services. ATM card has now become a prestigious issue.
3. Most of ATM users consist of educated people.
4. Middle class people are still away from this facility since most of the SB A/C holders are of middle class only.
5. Many customers are not familiar with the instructions about the ATM usage, for that reason they face many problems. Especially instructions like collecting the money/card within 15 seconds, if not collected money go back into the machine and the machine for security reasons captures card.
6. Most of the customers as well as bankers are of opinion that the numbers of ATMs points are more then sufficient to meet the current demands i.e., the supply is adequate.
7. Customers face problems with ATM transactions mainly due to their unawareness about the instructions of ATM usage. Hence bank employee need to educate the existing customers of ATM about there instructions and help them to reduce their problems and increase their level of satisfaction with the usage of ATM service.
8. In this study all categories of users (like age group, educational background, occupational and Annual Family Income) are highly satisfied with the ATM service, they rated this service as a excellent service.

Suggestions:

1. Awareness about the ATMs should be created among the customers/general public by adopting some promotional activities like giving free pompleints, sticking colorful wall posters in banks, giving an advertisement in the local cable network, conducting of work shop to accountholders etc.
2. Each ATM should be provided with a telephone with which customer can contact the bank personal at any time when he/she encountered with a problem in the ATM transaction.
3. The amount withdrawn per transaction and the amount withdrawn per day should be increased. As the more number of users of ATMs are business people they feel that the amount withdrawn per transaction or per day is too less.
4. A special consideration should be given to the heavy users of ATM services like some offerings or benefits or any discount coupons, so that they feel motivated to use the services more and more. And also a sense of belongingness with the bank will emerge in their mind.

References:

1. Prof.Ravi Shankar, "Services Marketing"the Indian Perspective-EXCEL Books, New Delhi-110002.
2. Atul Bhatt, "Banking Marketing –Marketing Research and Indian Banks" EXCEL Books ,New Delhi-2002.
3. Nalini Prava Tripathy "Financial Instruments and Services" PHI Pvt., New Delhi-2004.
4. M.Y.Khan "Financial Services ", IInd edition Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi-2001
5. Dr. V Gopalkrishnan,Head , Dept of Commerce, Tiruchendor 628216,Indian Journal of Marketing , May2005.
6. Vimal Sukumar, " Customer Satisfaction (20 Ways) to increase customer loyalty),Indian Journal of Commerce,June-2005.
7. Nataraj and Gordon , " Financial Markets and Services" Himalaya Publishing House , New Delhi-2004.
8. Parimal Uyas , " Customer Satisfaction – As a Core Competence ,Indian Journal of Marketing ,June-2005.
9. Dr. D.K.Agrawal "Service Marketing" Stop, Observe and Go,Indian Journal of Marketing ,June-2005 pp –12-28.
10. C.M.Chaudary , "A Banking and Finance" Malik and Company , Jipur-2003.

Annexure

Table No:1 :Age of Respondents

Age in year	Less than 25	25-35	35-45	45-55	More than 55	Total
No. of Respondents	24	46	18	6	6	100

Table No: 2: Education of Respondents

Education level	Middle	10+2	Graduate	Post graduate	Total
No.of Respondents	9	12	67	12	100

Table No:3: Profession of respondents

Occupation	Business	Senior Officer	Junior Officer	Clerk/Sales person	Student/Unemployment	Retired	Housewife	Total
No.of Respondents	30	12	18	6	28	6	--	100

Table No:4: Annual Family Income of Respondents

Income In Rs.	Less than 1500	15000-19999	20000-29999	30000-49999	50000-75000	More than 75000	Total
No.of Respondents	15	--	3	15	6	61	100

Table No: 5: Motivated Factor of Respondents

Motivator	Bank-employee	Friends	College	Self-Influenced	Total
No.of Respondents	49	18	--	33	100

Table No: 6: Period of Using the ATM Facility

Period	Less than Month	1-6 Month	6Month-1 Year	More than 1 Year	Total
No.of Respondents	--	67	9	24	100

Table No: 7: Average Visit to ATM

Frequency of ATM visit	1 st Visit	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Total
No.of Respondents	--	9	79	12	100

Table No: 8: Awareness about ATM Functioning or Usage

Response	Yes	No	Total
No.of Respondents	85	15	100

Table No: 9: Awareness about PIN

Persons	Yes	No	Total
No.of Respondents	97	3	100

Table No: 10: Checking the ATM Transitions in Passbook

Response	Yes	No	Total
No.of Respondents	55	45	100

Table No: 11: Amount Debited to Customers A/C without his Knowledge due to use of ATM

Response	Yes	No	Total
No.of Respondents	6%	94%	100

Table No: 12: Incidents wherein ATM restricted from transacting

Response	Yes	No	Total
No.of Respondents	9	91	100

Table No14whether the guard is trained enough to guide the customer

Response	Yes	No	Total
No.of Respondents	97	3	100

Table No: 15: Satisfaction with the availability of ATMs

	Satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Some what dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Total
No.of Respondents	55	39	--	6	100

Table No.16: Satisfaction with the availability of parking space at ATM

	Satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Some what dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Total
No.of Respondents	64	27	3	6	100

Table No.17: Rating of respondents about ATM usage

Rating	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Total
No.of Respondents	36	58	6	--	100